

MORPHOLOGY OF THE HEART IN PATIENTS WITH TUBERCULOSIS.

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Relevance of the topic: In the past, a person suffering from tuberculosis died regardless of his financial status and age. Today, this disease is not as scary as it was in the past. Despite all the advances in medicine, it can be overlooked, lost, and forgotten.

According to the World Health Organization, approximately 2.1 billion people worldwide are infected with tuberculosis. In 10% of them, tuberculosis may occur during their lifetime, in which AIDS is of great importance. The world's mass media say that the fight against tuberculosis is of global importance. It should also be said that the disease knows no borders. There is no way to stop the influx of tuberculosis patients, along with healthy people, into developed countries due to the development of relations between the populations of countries, migrations, and poverty.

The purpose of the work: as the purpose of the work, the aim of the work was to determine the morphological changes in the heart of the patients who died with various forms of tuberculosis at the Khorezm branch of the Scientific and Practical Medical Center of the Republic of Phthisiatry and Pulmonology.

The results obtained: within the framework of scientific research, the majority of patients suffering from various forms of tuberculosis were women, 70-80% of whom were examined by gender, and it was found that the disease was heart disease compared to other chronic diseases.

It was found that the patients brought to the Bureau of Pathological Anatomy of Khorezm Region who died of heart disease as a result of various types of tuberculosis had acute respiratory-cardiac failure.

CONCLUSIONS:

in conclusion, it can be said that among the diseases more common in women compared to men, tuberculosis is caused by morphological changes in the heart as a complication in various forms.

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